

A Study on Green Marketing and Its Product Availability in Tirunelveli District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Chandra, M. "A Study on Green Marketing and Its Product Availability in Tirunelveli District." Shanlax International Journal of Commerce, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 102–105.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461448>

M.Chandra

Ph.D. (Scholar), Sri Sarada College for Women, Tirunelveli

Abstract

Green marketing means selling the products and services. Which are environment friendly now-a-days. Green marketing is more popular because most of the people are becoming conscious in saving the environmental. Though the green marketing is very expensive many people are willing to use environment friendly products. Green marketing raise the voice against the production and consumption threatens peaceful life of human being on the earth.

Reducing use of plastics and plastics-based products. The business activities firms about pollution control and production of eco-friendly products. The researcher made the study about the green market and the product availability in Tirunelveli district. The researcher analyzed 80 respondents from the same area.

Keywords: Green marketing strategy, environment strategy, stakeholder analysis, competitors, awareness.

Introduction

Green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Thus green marketing incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising. Defining green marketing is not a simple task where several meanings intersect and contradict each other; an example of this will be the existence of varying social, environmental and retail definitions attached to this term. Other similar terms used are Environmental Marketing and Ecological Marketing. So, in this scenario of global concern, corporate houses have taken green marketing as a visible part of their strategic planning to promote products by employing environmental claims either about their attributes or about their systems, policies and processes of the firm that manufacture or sell them. Green marketing is part and parcel of overall corporate strategy; along with manipulating the traditional marketing mix, it requires an understanding of the public policy process. So, we can say green marketing covers a broad range of activities. "Green or Environmental Marketing consists of all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants, such that the satisfaction of these needs and wants occurring with minimal detrimental impact on the natural environment."

Green marketing involves developing and promoting products and services that satisfy customers' wants and desires for Quality, Performance, Affordable Pricing and Convenience without having a detrimental input on the environment. Most of the people in the Tirunelveli district are conscious of the environment, so the study is based on green market products and its availability in Tirunelveli district.

Objectives

1. To Study the attitude of consumers towards green marketing.
2. To establish a relationship between consumer purchasing decision and green marketing.
3. To develop a suitable green marketing mix for consumers and companies.
4. To identify consumers behavior towards Quality of product, Green advertising, and green labeling.
5. To highlight the opportunities challenges being faced by consumer & companies.

Scope

The scope of the study revolves around only in the consumer point of view. It covers the area of product availability in the Tirunelveli area.

Methodology

The primary data have been collected directly from respondents about the availability of products, goods and services through the questionnaire. Secondary data have been collected from standard books, articles, magazines, encyclopedia and internet.

Primary Data

The study mainly based upon the primary data. Interview schedule method is used to collect the data from the respondents. The sample size of "100" respondents have been appended in the research report.

Secondary Data

The substantiate and to support the primary data required particular have been gathered by referring the reputed journals, magazines, standard news paper and book, some of the information has been gathered from authorized web source.

Analysis of Data

Table 1

Gender	No of Respondent	Percentage
Male	100	67
Female	50	33
Total	150	100
Age	No of Respondent	Percentage
Below 25 years	54	36
25-35 years	43	29
35-45 years	38	25
45-55 years	10	7
Above 55 years	5	10

Total	150	100
Monthly income	No of Respondent	Percentage
Below Rs 25000	58	39
Rs 25000-35000	40	27
Rs 35000-45000	37	24
Above Rs 45000	15	10
Total	150	100
Educational qualification	No of Respondent	Percentage
High secondary	54	36
Graduate	43	29
Post Graduate	35	23
Professionals	11	7
Others	7	5
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 1, shows that out of 150 respondents 67 percentage of the respondents are male, Next 36 percentage of the respondents are under age group below 25 years, Next 39 percentage of the respondents are under monthly income of below Rs.25000. Next 36 percentages of the respondents are Higher secondary.

Table 2 Types of Satisfaction By The Customers

Particular	Total	Mean Score	Rank
Product Satisfaction	585	39	II
Satisfaction with Purchase Decision	571	38	III
Satisfaction with the Performance Attribute	601	40	I
Satisfaction with the Store or Institution	559	37.6	IV
Satisfaction with the Purchase Experience	557	37.1	V

Source: Primary Data

Ranks reveal that majority of the respondent. The first rank was given to Satisfaction with the performance attribute with mean score of 40, Second rank was given to Product satisfaction with mean score of 39, third rank was given to Satisfaction with purchase decision with mean score to 38, Fourth rank was given to Satisfaction with the store or institution with mean score to 37.6, Fifth rank was given to Satisfaction with the purchase experience with mean score to 37.1 ranks respectively.

Findings

The finding of the present revealed the following.

- The majority of the respondents are male with 67%.
- The majority of the respondent's age group lay down below 25 years with 36%.
- The majority of the respondents were laid on below 25000 monthly incomes with 39%.
- The majority of the respondent's educational qualification on higher secondary with 36%.
- Satisfaction with the performance attribute scored the first rank with the mean score in 40.

Suggestion

- The above modern techniques lead to increasing the level of achievement of the concern.
- It yields time-saving. Attracting the customer in the shorter period.
- Even though it gives the profitability to the firms, the advertisement must have some social responsibilities. So it must be the favor to both firms as well as customer, then only it gives much effective.

Conclusion

Green marketing should not neglect the economic aspect of marketing. Marketers need to understand the implications of green marketing. If marketers think customers are not concerned about environmental issues or will not pay a premium for products that are more eco-responsible, then they should think again. Marketers must find an opportunity to enhance their products. Although Green Marketing Myopia is another challenge for the marketers, it is the fundamental responsibility of the Marketers to innovate and adopt new marketing strategies those would safeguard our eco system as well as satisfy the customers.

References

- Marketing Management, Keller, Koshy, Jha, 13th Edition, Kotler, Pearson Prentice Hall Publication.
Marketing Management, Analysis, Kotler Philip, 9th Edition, Prentice Hall India Publication.
The Business Standard, Dt. 30.11.09, “CSR makes good ‘business case.’”
The Business Standard, Dt. 16.12.09, “Omfed packets to harp on energy conservation.”
The Business Standard, Dt.08.12.09, “Small Car maker, but big energy saver.”
The Business Standard, Dt.07.12.09, “L&T ‘sensors’ climate change.”
<http://www.seminarprojects.com/Green-Marketing>
<http://www.bnet.com>

Web Sources

- <http://apjor.com/files/1384068705.pdf>
<http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.404.638&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
<http://www.iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/UploadFolder/Exploring%20Factors-2-3-4/Exploring%20Factors-2-3-4.pdf>
<http://www.trp.org.in/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ARSS-Vol.6-No.1-January-June-2017-pp.6-9.pdf>
<https://slidex.tips/download/a-study-of-the-impact-of-green-marketing-practices-on-consumer-buying-behaviour>
<https://www.coursehero.com/file/p31n6mf/consumers-all-over-the-world-is-concerned-about-this-common-threat-of-global/>
https://www.westeastinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/ZIKRI-MUHMMAD1-MUHAMAD-FERDHAUS-SAZALI2-_AZIZ-ABDUL.pdf